

CHILDREN FOR IMMUNOSTIMULANT PREPARATIONS APPLICATION USE AND MEANING**Rano Nuraliyeva**

Samarkand State Medical University, assistant professor of clinical pharmacology department.

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Abstract. *If the child per year six times more and coolness with occurring often to colds inclined if it is , it is a lot cases ill is medical to the list is taken . Such children for immunostimulation doer preparations most of the time offer will be done . Various different content and they come out . Such tools vegetable , interferon and to bacteria is divided , their in the composition vaccine such as dead bacteria microdoses there is*

Keywords : *Natural immunostimulant and immunomodulators , Immunomodulators main groups , from immunomodulators Use of immunostimulants preparation*

Аннотация. *Если ребенок в год в шесть раз больше и прохлады с часто встречающимися простудными заболеваниями склонна, если она есть, то много случаев заболевания берется в медицинский список. Таким детям для иммуностимуляции чаще всего будут делать препараты. Разный разный контент и они выходят. Такие средства делятся на растительные, интерфероновые и бактериальные, их в составе вакцины мертвые микродозы бактерий нет.*

Ключевые слова : *Природные иммуностимуляторы и иммуномодуляторы , Основные группы иммуномодуляторов , из иммуномодуляторов Использование препарата иммуностимуляторов*

Plant sources children for immunostimulant

Most cheap and often applied drugs medicine to plants based on Of them some of them past century since long from time since used , but this own importance and the effect did not lose . To this the following includes :

- China magnolia vine branch The drug one for how many months doctor showed scheme according to interruptions with is taken . Schisandra adults and children for drug tools in the form of and new to those who relatively good to immunity have
- Eleutherococcus 2-3 times a day using the baby life 1 drop every year gives Agent water with diluted and from feeding after is given ;
- Ginseng tincture 30 days during vegetables acceptance and then the same that's it take a break done increases ;
- Echinacea antique from the period since applied and do not drip in the form of or him own into will receive tools as use can Immunostimulant to the effect have and organism negative to factors adapts ;
- Immune liquid and tablet in the form there is In drops stomach , ARI and contagious diseases prevention get , treat and childbirth probability reduce for to babies is given The drug contains Echinacea purpurea extract there is Up to 6 years old has been children 5-10 drops 2-3 times per day , from food before water with diluted .

Interferon group children for immunostimulator

This of the group all medicines treatment in the process immunity increases . Especially theirs of infection in the beginning , as well as prevention for them current to do important From interferon received addict to substances the following includes :

- Arbidol - 2 years acceptance to do for capsules ;
- Grippferon , Anaferon - infectious diseases and contagious diseases in the spread active an antiviral drug ;
- Leukocytes interferon - the nose grow up and instillation to do for dry is substance . Of the disease the first hours effective

Bacterial come output children for immunostimulant substances

Children for good of immunostimulants list the following was :

- IRS-19 - ENT members diseases prevention get for to the organism active effect showing nose for disruptive actions , bronchitis , rhinitis , tonsillitis , rhinopharyngitis , etc including and allergic come output Three from the moon starting from measures set ;
- Imudon - throat and in the mouth local immunity to increase directed Russian work of producers tablets . Tonsillitis , stomatitis and bronchitis with hurt of patients most of them for suitable coming (falling infection due to);
- Broncho munal broncho-pulmonary system diseases treatment and prevention get for capsules ;
- Ribomunil babies often to the cold resistant to be for 6 months since is used .

Small children more to adults than Cold to be can At home from being according to children in kindergarten contract to do danger big Of this because of the children immunities from conception starting from and the child is 14-16 years old until enough is formed . The same at the time of the child health healthy without save , his to the body harm failure to deliver need Children for how immunostimulants to use recommendation will be done ?

WHEN TO USE IMMUNOSTIMULATORS

Immunity support task of parents in front flu , mouth pain or with ARVI when he got sick rises . The majority addict substances alone leave they think that it won't happen and they are error does not However , children immunostimulants only doctor with it is necessary to consult tests from submission after get need Only expert immunologist growing of the organism situation right assessment and right medicines determine can Family members autoimmune to diseases played parents especially caution to be should : this without to the child immunostimulants acceptance to do is strictly prohibited . This diseases between rheumatic arthritis , diffuse toxic meat , to insulin related diabetes mellitus, vitiligo, multiple sclerosis , lupus erythematosus , bronchial asthma and some another diseases enters Such medicines constant respectively get need no , they are of the child developing inviolability harm deliver can

TYPES OF IMMUNOSTIMULATORS

Children for immunostimulants not only drugs , maybe plant , natural elements is also Naturally , honey , propolis, garlic , sweet red pepper , carrot, fat very famous All this side effects of products about without worrying (only allergic if not) eat they can Entirely is safe . That's it separately note reach must be honey one from the age starting from to the children to be given can also garlic cooked , raw garlic three from since consumption will be done .

Children for another immunostimulants plant extracts and plant infusions is considered This drinks previous as in food is harmless , therefore for you to the doctor of herbs use about advice give need Most famous tinctures echinacea , in myocardium root , ginseng , rhodiola rosea , hawthorn , China magnolia grapes , chamomile , parsnip , celandine , eucalyptus and from coltsfoot work is issued . They are selenium trace elements own into takes , they antibodies work exit encourages and to tumors against efficient will fight

With medicine drug tools own into received children for immunostimulants work is released :

- " Transfer Factor Kids ";
- " Derinat ";
- " Viferon ";
- " Interferon ";
- " Arbidol ";
- Anaferon ;
- " Cycloferon ";
- " Immunal ";
- " Bronchocommunal ";
- Oscillocoxin .

This of drugs never one to the child doctor without appointment It is not given in the comment what from being strictly look , however this drugs familiar that knows _

HOW TO USE IMMUNOSTIMULATORS?

Many of pediatricians to his opinion according to the children for only immunostimulants constant immunity formation contribution does not add : of the child healthy marriage style for conditions Create need This done increase for to eat balancing , positive feelings surface release , complete to sleep and rest to get time separate need Your children never how without medication healthy let it be

Immunomodulator and immunostimulant

Immunity a person organism very thin protection is a system and sometimes qualified to fix need Of this for special preparations intended - immunomodulator and immunostimulant . Both drug tool one different to mechanisms effect does , but of the process essence different

Immunostimulants and immunomodulators differences

Our immunity certain from directions consists of bacteria , infections or to viruses against to fight in response work developed different different cells is a set . Such cells the number less , especially in epidemics often to morbidity take will come

Long term chronic diseases due to protection system usually not working normally puts this connections slowly or no has been inflammation with work is issued . Such cases they are body cells to themselves attack when you do autoimmune diseases about they speak

Immunomodulators from immunostimulants difference does :

1. Protection cell connection deficiency with organism a lot amount work to issue forced to do need Of this for immunostimulant is used .
2. Autoimmune diseases big and small cells number balance requires correction . In this case immunomodulators , as well as immunosuppressors own into takes - defense connections work release interrupter substances .

Perhaps immunomodulators _ and of immunostimulants differences small to the list have because they are the same so to the goal directed drugs - immunity fix

Immunostimulants preparation

This kind of drug tools apply the following cases is displayed :

- immunity of scarcity main conditions ;

- malignant plants ;
- fungal , viral or bacterial infection because of come coming out repeated relapses with passing chronic chronic diseases ;

- secondary immunity deficiency status with any that provoke pathology .

Modern of immunostimulants classification :

- of the organism to himself special didn't happen resistance stimulants (pentoxyl , prodigiosan , sodium Nuclein , methyluracil);

- humorous immune reactions stimulants (splenin , myopid);

- cellular immunities stimulants (Leakadin , Timoptin , Molgamostin) .

From immunomodulators use

Your body defense system corrective tools the following problems solution to do for recommendation will be :

- allergic reactions ;
- organ transplantation ;
- lymphocytes of cells activity ;
- Autoimmune diseases .

Immunomodulators main groups :

- probiotic microorganisms (bifidobacteria , propionic acid bacteria , lactobacteril);

- cytostatics ;

- hormone preparations ;

- of antibiotics some types (rapamycin , cyclosporine);

- antilymphocytic globulins ;

- monoclonal antibodies ;

- anti-Rh-immunoglobulins .

Natural immunostimulant and immunomodulators

Highlight ok , even chronic diseases and to infections strong effect if too , seeing outgoing of groups medicines acceptance to do always too necessary not _ Your body defense system many natural drugs and of plants infusions using complete himself restores _

Immunity correction the following natural products using done increase can :

- carob pistachios ;
- pumpkin ;
- garlic ;
- beans (soy , peas and red beans);
- Selenium quantity high has been grains ;
- the sea products ;
- milk ;
- olive oil ;
- pistachios ;
- echinacea ;
- honey
- nettle grass
- propolis ;

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